

Effectiveness of Urban Renewal Strategies Adopted for Urban Development in Enugu Urban, Enugu State

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effectiveness of Urban Renewal Strategies adopted for urban development in Enugu Metropolis. Specific objectives included ascertaining the effectiveness of the strategies adopted and analysing the negative and positive impacts on the people and environment. The survey research design was adopted for the study as it enabled the efficient collection and reviewing of data from the respondents. Questionnaire constituted the data collection instrument. Frequencies, percentages, means and Goal Achievement Matrix (GAM) were employed in analyzing the study's data. Major findings revealed that the urban renewal strategy adopted in coal camp and Agu-Owa (redevelopment and rehabilitation respectively) were more effective than that adopted in Ikirike (redevelopment). From the study, it was also revealed that the impacts of urban renewal in coal camp area included property damage/loss, loss of means of livelihood, household displacement; upgrade in environmental conditions; increased land value; improved infrastructure, roads and buildings; stability in the economy of coal camp and improved job opportunities. The result of the hypothesis test concluded that the impacts of adopted urban renewal strategies were statistically significant in the study area as the p-value (0.0001) was less than the level of significance (0.05) adopted for the study. Major recommendation of the study states that further review of renewed sites like Ikirike, Agu-Owa and Coal camp should be undertaken. This is to ensure that project objectives are realized.

Keywords: Urban Renewal, Development, Rehabilitation, Redevelopment, Enugu Urban

1.0. Introduction

In many countries around the world, as the population grows, the environment becomes congested and the accessible social amenities are used beyond their intended purpose, creating urban problems that may lead to urban rejuvenation. The process of reviving a deteriorating built environment neighborhood in order to boost local economy and safety is known as urban renewal, or UR (Agunbiade, 2017). Because of its versatility, UR can be applied to both development and redevelopment. Urban Redevelopment (UR) is an initiative involving land rehabilitation in areas of modest to high volume urban land use. It is commonly referred to as urban redevelopment or renewal in the United Kingdom (Agbola, 2017). This occurs when a deliberate plan to enhance an area includes rebuilding the physical social and economic features of a dilapidated metropolitan area. In many nations, typical regeneration initiatives include housing, industrial sites, and dockside developments (Jonlang, 2020).

Urban regeneration, according to Kabiru (2019), usually encompasses social and economic activity in addition to the physical growth of a place. The majority of developing nations, including Nigeria, India, the Philippines, South Africa, Brazil, Hong Kong, and Bangladesh, have seen fast population increase and urban sprawl. Furthermore, it should be mentioned that the majority of Nigerian cities were developed prior to the creation of provincial governance and city growth (Oyesiku, 2018). In fact, over 60% of Nigeria's population would live in urban areas, as reported by the United Nations (UN, 2018). Between 2009 and 2019, the percentage of people living in urban areas increased from 42.5 percent to 51.16 percent. Statista, 2021. High rates of overcrowding, traffic, pollution, inadequate housing and a home, filth neglect,

and rising rates of poverty and crime are some of the characteristics that define the urbanization issue in emerging nations (Jiboye and Omoniyi, 2019). One of the fundamental characteristics of the problems is the variability of Nigerian cities with respect to their size, order, geometric shape, economy, wealth, and availability of local resources (Owoputi, 2016; Olokesusi, 2016). Despite having one of the poorest Human Development Indexes (HDIs) in the world, it is predicted that 87 percent of Africa's population increase would occur in its cities over the next 20 years (Daramola and Ibem, 2019).

With a population of about 200 million, Nigeria is currently overrun by fast urbanization, inadequate infrastructure, and a growing array of urban slums nationwide. In the years to come, this number is predicted to rise dramatically. The deterioration of urban infrastructure has made urban residents more vulnerable to environmental threats (Gbadegesin and Aluko, 2019). Physical development plans are lacking in many cities and villages, and their execution is subpar. Nigerian cities suffer from unauthorized commercial, industrial, and residential developments (Gbadegesin and Aluko, 2019). The city of Enugu is home to a number of slums as well as squatter communities that lack proper lighting, water, garbage disposal, and sanitation. Due to the lack of a suitable framework to address the detrimental effects, urban expansion and a rise in the number of people entering Enugu State have led to the formation of these slums. In Nigeria, policymakers and urban renewal authorities have made token gestures toward the successful participation of slum dwellers in urban regeneration initiatives for their housing. Residents were perceived as a mostly passive group of objects that were unable to influence governmental entities politically or respond to public concerns (Back, 2016). Through their level of cooperation, opposition, and final choice to adapt as well as accept modifications to their living space, slum dwellers may actively participate in the revitalization process. Well-meaning renewal initiatives in Nigeria failed because of the slum dwellers' lack of participation. For example, the Maroko residents' resistance to the recommended 1990 Maroko evacuation project is one of the reasons that has hindered

the scheme to this day. In a similar vein, Onibokun (2018) details how the government's proposed regeneration programs for some areas of Ibadan failed miserably because the populace vehemently rebelled opposed them and immediately prepared a showdown if the renewal programs were implemented.

The government was forced to abandon the plan. The narrative is similar in Port Harcourt, where a large-scale riot by locals and other stakeholders paralyzed and stopped the planned renovation program for the core sections.

The majority of Nigerians living in cities do not yet understand the value of urban redevelopment as a strategy to stop environmental degradation. This has affected the urban population's capacity for adaptation, especially that of low-income urban settlers. As a result, sufficient awareness campaigns are needed in urban areas to inform residents about the need of urban regeneration for environmental sustainability. Thus, the efficiency of the urban redevelopment initiatives used in Enugu Metropolis was the main emphasis of this study.

1.1.Study Hypothesis

The negative and positive impacts of urban renewal on the people and environment of Enugu Metropolis are not statistically significant

2.0. Review of Literature

2.1Concepts

i.Urban Renewal

Originally intended to clear and restructure inner-city land use slums for an entire novel dwelling and non-residential development program, urban renewal is an idea of urban redevelopment that originated in America with the Housing Act of 1949 (Sanmi, Oluwasogo, and Agboola, 2021). It is a normative notion, according to Robert and Skye (2017), with roots in British governance for urban issues with the goal of bringing about long-lasting improvements and changes in the areas of economic, physical, social, and environmental circumstances. According to Agbola (2017), urban renewal is an all-encompassing community redevelopment program that a city uses to reimagine and reconstruct the physical structures of a specific area of the city in order to better address the issues it faces.

According to Weaver (2020), urban renewal is the culmination of both governmental and private initiatives that delay or end urban obsolescence, stop degradation, remove undesirable areas, and improve structures, infrastructure, and the surroundings that possess some usable life left. Wood (1967) summed it up as a system for avoiding urban neighborhoods from becoming prematurely obsolete, as well as facilities for revitalizing deteriorating regions and revitalizing worn-out places.

According to Olawepo (2018), urban regeneration is the act of improving the structure and standing of a certain area of a community in order to modernize it and make it "new." City expanding and redevelopment, thorough road development and redesign, landscaping and settlement layout, facility upgrades, drainage system construction within an urban center, and implementing improving slums and city development are the main components of a renewal program (Malik and Azeez, 2015).

ii. Urban Renewal Strategies

One definition of urban renewal is the process of improving and rehabilitating an urban neighborhood or region, or a method of planning focused on the physical enhancement of a current urban settlement using any of the methods listed below: restoration, conservation, and preservation; or redevelopment, upgrading, or regeneration. These techniques have been regarded as urban redevelopment initiatives.

i. Redevelopment

Redevelopment is the process of completely clearing an area and halting its deterioration. This method of clearing slums and creating a better one based on a new blueprint is sometimes referred to as a bulldozer approach. This strategy has been used in Nigerian cities to guarantee total slum clearance. Due to aging, Nigerian towns are made up of deteriorated environmental quality and physical infrastructure (Adepoju, 2017). The goal of this technique is to ensure that slums and unlawful constructions constructed on highways or service areas are removed.

ii. Rehabilitation

This method entails restoring a structure or environment that is degrading to its original usage and creating the site and service

arrangements that are required. This approach, which may be used to individual buildings or to outmoded structures, involves repurposing buildings or regions without completely destroying the structure (Valent-Pereira, 2016). Because rehabilitation involves less and less destruction, this approach is utilized to restore sections of government buildings that are physically sound but cannot afford to be redeveloped. To maximize the use of public funds, this plan just requires the upgrading of buildings and infrastructure.

iii. Upgrading

By offering infrastructure and essential services, the approach aims to enhance. This strategy involves the World Bank's assistance and the government's intervention. Additionally, to environmental improvement programs and social services like drainage, garbage disposal, collecting waste, hospitals, markets, recreational areas, etc., the government is expected to supply and finance infrastructure such as water, accessible roads via pedestrian pathways, and electricity. People will be able to further enhance the way they live on their own initiative with the support of soft loans and proper environmental orientation. The Amman, Jordan, squatter colony upgrade project was funded by the World Bank in collaboration with Save the Children Federation's community development.

iv. Regeneration

Urban regeneration is aimed at the simultaneous change of physical fabric, social structures, and environmental conditions of an environment. Roberts and Skye (2017) provides an initial definition of urban regeneration 'comprehensive and integrated vision and action which leads to the resolution of urban problems and which seeks to bring about a lasting improvement in the economic, physical, social, and environmental conditions of an area that has been subject to change' (see Figure 2.1). Public regeneration initiatives seek to improve impoverished communities by attempting to eliminate obvious issues, but they also affect families who are attempting to foster the feeling of community by clinging to familiar people and places. The difference between neighborhood and community circumstances is evident during regeneration (UN-HABITAT, 2010). A great instance is the

committee that was established to clean up the Ogonland land in the Ogon Niger Delta in response to the government's announcement in a news report in 2016. The project is expected to take up to 20 years to complete.

Figure 2.1: Concept of Urban Regeneration
Source: Roberts and Skye (2017)

v. Revitalization

By controlling hygienic conditions, revitalization aims to enhance urban living circumstances. The preservation of limited resources and environmental protection require a thorough, long-term strategy that looks at and manages the various factors influencing contemporary cities (Goncalves, 2016). From a condition of deterioration, revitalization serves to restore the environment's vitality, vitality, and activity. This may be accomplished with a thorough strategy that is updated often. Zoning laws, subdivision rules, while creating and residential codes that set requirements for land use and construction quality are some of the legal instruments that give the plan its day-to-day expression.

Vi. Conservation

This is the process of keeping structures or urban features in excellent physical condition due to the preservation of its architectural, cultural, and historical significance. Protecting and maintaining urban areas in a way that enhances their civic, financial, and environmental sustainability is known as urban conservation (Megan, 2022). These consist of the emir's palace, a mosque, a cathedral, the old Hausa city walls of Kano with its grand arched gates, etc. This tactic has been used to shield the environment from potential harm

and prevent additional degradation. The fundamental objective of preserving these historical monuments is to keep its character intact and prevent them from disappearing because of the area's historical or aesthetic significance or associated urban design features. The best method for physically designing solutions to environmental issues without harming the built environment is this one.

vii. Preservation

Structures, towns, biodiversity, fertile soil, air and water that is pure, mineral riches, and fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas are all examples of natural resources that should be preserved. Buildings and cities are conserved or recognized as landmarks. The building supplies and techniques utilized in historic structures are the focus of architectural preservationists. While the exteriors of some of these buildings may remain unchanged, others may have their interiors modified to suit a different purpose, such as when sizable private estates are turned into museums. In order to portray a cohesive whole or a historic atmosphere, houses are frequently decorated in accordance with their time period (Eduardo-Rojas, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Inclinations of the Study

Theoretical inclinations as reviewed for the current study were presented in this subsection.

i. Theory of Sustainable Development

"Sustainable Development" as a concept dates back to the 1970s. "Development" was defined as the technique of balanced and integrated growth of both humans and environment at the UN's Conference regarding Human Environment's Declaration, which was held in Stockholm, Sweden, in 1972. The idea of sustainable development—the capacity to fulfill present-day demands without sacrificing the happiness of future generations—was articulated in 1987 during a meeting of the International Commission on Environment and Development, which was headed by Brundtland.

Urban development has been influenced by the integration of sustainable development since the 1990s (Couch, Sykes, and Borstinghaus, 2011). This integration emphasizes the importance of coordinating different elements at the ecological, economic, and social levels

in order to promote the growth of cities (Gregorio and Seixas, 2017). In the meanwhile, urban redevelopment incorporates the idea of green rejuvenation (Sousa, 2018).

ii. Smart Growth Theory

The United States state of Maryland initially put up the idea of "Smart Growth" in 1997 in response to a number of issues brought on by the expansion of agriculture, environmental degradation, and the stark split of socioeconomic classes. The American Planning Association partnered with 60 public organizations to create "Smart Growth America" in 2000. Focusing on a wide range of concerns related to quality of life, smart growth aims to reduce urban sprawl by designing and constructing compact communities, making the most of the efficiency of current infrastructure, offering a wider variety of housing and transportation alternatives, etc. The arrangement urban spatial development idea is embodied in Smart Growth Theory, which enables the city to expand more sustainably and connotatively through innovative planning and design techniques including defining the urban growth limit.

In the United States, smart growth is now a strategy for creating cities and communities that are socially just, economically successful, and ecologically sustainable.

iii. New Urbanism Theory

In response to the numerous issues brought about by the growth of cities, the concept of "New Urbanism" was established in the 1980s. In order to prevent the spread of urban sprawl, new urbanism highlights the impact of urban form, considers the importance of urban growth, and promotes learning from the United States' pre-World War II small town planning experience. Regional planning is valued by new urbanism, which emphasizes addressing and resolving issues at the regional level. People-centeredness is given additional weight in new urbanism, which emphasizes the livability of the built environment and the experiences and feelings of its inhabitants.

It also promotes reverence for nature and history, stressing that human, natural, and historical harmony should be preserved in urban planning, design, and building. By creating high-density, superior urban spatial structures like Traditional Neighborhood

growth (TND) and Transit-oriented Development (TOD), new urbanism encourages urban sustainable growth. However, it offers sensible recommendations for design and intensity development to support community sustainability and self-renewal.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

In this subsection, the works of previous authors were examined. An investigation on the effects of urban renewal (UR) on the construction sector of Nigeria's Abuja Metropolis was carried out by Adefemi et al. in 2022. The purpose of the study was to look into the advantages and disadvantages of UR for Nigeria's built environment. To achieve the aim of the research, the study adopted a qualitative research method. The study's conclusions show that UR affects Nigeria's capital city in both good and bad ways. Improvements to the environment, economic stability, and a growth in the value of infrastructure and property are some of the benefits.

On the other hand, the drawbacks include economic hardship, property losses of N17 billion, displacement (more than 700,000 people have been uprooted from new areas over the last 20 years), and exorbitant land and infrastructure costs. Major economic losses, according to the research, include the N100 billion loss of community facilities and infrastructure. However, according to the authors, measures including community involvement, fair compensation, government legislation, and execution were created to lessen the detrimental effects of UR on the structure itself.

Shach-Pinsly (2022) examined the effects of multi-parametric assessment on district regeneration in Israel using three urban renewal techniques for one national blueprint plan, TAMA38. This strategy was created to make individual structures more earthquake-resistant, but it also acts as a spur for the renovation of dilapidated individual homes in older communities, especially in areas with strong demand. This study's goal was to evaluate the performance of three urban sites created in the city of Haifa under the TAMA38 program using three primary approaches: (1) a single comprehensive plan with a single developer and different building locations; (2) a single comprehensive plan

with a variety of developers but with the same building locations; and (3) oneself building renewals without a comprehensive plan. This analysis's technique was founded on assessing a number of quality and quantitative factors that affect the built environment's performance. The study's findings highlight the necessity of selecting an urban renewal plan that is specific to a given area and the requirement that the authority be in charge of organizing open public areas at every stage of the process.

A research on urban renewal techniques for redesigning the Tudun-Ilu neighborhood in Kaduna, Nigeria, was carried out by Hassan (2023). The purpose of this study was to assess the various urban regeneration strategies and recommend the most effective one for Tudun Ilu. Qualitative as well as quantitative studies approaches served as the foundation for the study methodology. Inadequate amenities, overcrowding, deteriorating structures, multiple land uses, conflicts between pedestrians and vehicles, disorganized spacious areas using missing spaces for recreation, poor drainage channels that cause flooding during rainy seasons, haphazard waste disposal, poor sewage systems, and a poor road network are just a few of the environmental issues that the research identified. The analysis concludes by suggesting the most effective urban redevelopment plan to direct the region's growth, which will significantly address the physical issues in comparable towns.

Adedeji and Azeez (2015) investigated how regeneration techniques affected the city of Ibadan. The study included primary as well as secondary data sources. Due to the large concentration of renewal programs in these LGAs, five (5) LGAs, or 45.45%, were purposefully chosen. According to the analysis's findings, 47.2%, 36.4%, and 9.6% of the participants, respectively, stated that the renewal programs had a favorable, negative, and both effects on them. Additionally, 51.9%, 50.2%, 46.4%, and 47.2% of those surveyed said that access to recreational amenities, safe water, and environmental cleanliness had all increased as a result of road building. As a result, the research suggests that these programs be maintained and included in state government policy papers both within and outside of the study region. People's living situations will be improved as a result. The

current study would close the locational gap from the empirical review by attempting to assess the efficacy of urban revitalization initiatives with a focus on Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

3.0.Methods

The study's survey research approach was chosen because it made it possible to gather and analyze respondent data in an effective manner. A questionnaire served as the study's data collecting tool, and information was gathered from both primary and secondary sources. For the investigation, basic random sample methods and purposeful sampling were used. Three locations—Ikirike, Agu-Owa, and CoalCamp—where prior urban redevelopment initiatives have been carried out were selected for the research. Purposive sampling meant that only those who lived in Enugu Metropolis or were employed as physical planners were chosen for the sample. The study used simple random sampling to guarantee all the respondents were selected at random, eliminating any possibility of bias. On this note, a sample size of 397 was obtained whilst utilizing the Taro Yameni (1976) formula. Frequencies, percentages, means and Goal Achievement Matrix (GAM) were employed in analyzing the study's data.

4.0.Findings

4.1Analysis of the effectiveness of the strategies adopted during urban renewal in Enugu Metropolis

To achieve this objective, the researchers formulated objectives that are achievable by a good urban renewal scheme. The objectives of each adopted strategy were evaluated using the Goal Achievement Matrix (GAM). The objectives were rated by the respondents and the highest value rating showed that such strategy was adequate.

From table 1, the results showed the effectiveness of the adopted strategies of urban renewal in selected areas in Enugu City. From the analysis, results showed that the adopted strategy for Coal camp (redevelopment) (scoring 27 out of 35) and Agu-Owa (redevelopment and rehabilitation) (scoring 27 out of possible 35) was more effective than the adopted strategy for Ikirike (redevelopment).

Table 1: Evaluation of Urban renewal strategies in selected areas of Enugu Metropolis

S/N	Objectives	Ikirike	Agu-owa	Coal camp
1	Impact on local economy	4	4	5
2	Culturally adequate	4	5	2
3	Sustainability of achieved outcomes	3	3	4
4	Improvement in living conditions	4	4	4
5	Cost effectiveness	4	4	4
6	Entrenchment of orderliness in developmental activities	3	3	4
7	Attraction of good and viable social and physical infrastructure	3	4	4
	Total	25	27	27

Keys: 5: Very able to achieve objectives, 4: Able to achieve objectives; 3: Moderately able to achieve objectives; 2: Little able to achieve objectives; 1: Not able to achieve objectives

Source: Field Survey, 2025

This result further corroborates that of Adewale and Afolabi (2017) who averred that the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents greatly influences the perception and success of urban renewal in any area. Also, the result is in line with that of Adepaju (2017) who opined that the strategies of urban renewal yield differing outcomes in different locations. He further advised that town planners and other executors evaluate each strategy before its implementation so as to yield desired result.

4.2. Analysis of the negative and positive impacts of urban renewal on the people and environment of Enugu Metropolis

From table 2, results showed that all the identified impacts of urban renewal were significant in the study area as they all scored mean scores above 1.49. From the analysis,

property damage/loss (m= 2.80) and loss of means of livelihood (m= 2.80) accounted as the major impacts in Enugu during the urban renewal project. This was followed by household displacement (m= 2.44); upgrade in environmental conditions (m= 2.23); increased land value (m= 2.19); improved infrastructure, roads and buildings (m= 2.11); stability in the economy of coal camp (m= 2.07) and improved job opportunities (m= 1.80). This result showed that the undertaken urban renewal project had both negative and positive impacts in Enugu metropolis. This result corroborates that of Adefemi et al (2022), Uwadiogwu and Iyi (2013), Shach-Pinsly (2023), Adedeji and Arayela (2017) and Ibem et al (2022) who averred that urban renewal had notable impacts on the environment. From these authors, the impacts ranged from loss of properties, household displacement, increased land value among others.

Table 2: Impact of urban renewal in Enugu Metropolis (N= 376)

S/N	Impacts	A 3	INDIF 2	D 1	Mean	Rank
1	Upgrade in environmental conditions	187	87	102	2.23	Accepted
2	Stability in the economy of coal camp	164	76	136	2.07	Accepted
3	Increased land value	195	59	122	2.19	Accepted
4	Household displacement	256	30	90	2.44	Accepted
5	Property damage/loss	312	54	10	2.80	Accepted
6	Loss of means of livelihood	319	34	23	2.80	Accepted
7	Improved infrastructure, roads and building	187	45	144	2.11	Accepted
8	Improved job opportunities	108	86	182	1.80	Accepted

Keys: A = Agree; INDIF = Indifferent; D = Disagree

Source: Field Survey, 2026

4.3. Testing Hypothesis

The negative and positive impacts of urban renewal on the people and environment of Enugu Metropolis are not statistically significant. In testing the study's hypothesis, the values from Table 2 were inputted into the computer with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 and the results with a degree of freedom of 9 and a significance level of 0.05 was obtained.

Pearson's Chi-square = 1.212^a

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Asymp. Sig. (2-sided) also known as the p-value = >0.001

Decision Rule:

Accept H_0 , if Chi-square P-value is greater than significance level (α) value and reject H_0 if otherwise

Conclusion:

P-value (Asymptotic) = $p > 0.001$

α value = 0.05

Therefore, H_0 is rejected because p-value is < (less than) α value which is 0.05, also, difference between the observed and expected count are significantly different.

Also, Cramer's V value of .604 shows a high correlation between variables, this means that the impacts and the significance on the people and the environment was strongly correlated.

Implication:

The Implication of this result is that the Alternative hypothesis (H_1) was upheld, which states that the negative and positive impacts of urban renewal on the people and environment of Enugu Metropolis are statistically significant.

5.0. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

With a focus on Enugu, this research assessed urban regeneration tactics. The study also looked at the activity's effects on the environment and people in the coal camp, both good and bad. The results of the study showed that the socioeconomic traits of the respondents affected how the program was seen and how successful it was. The study also showed that between 2008 and 2013, urban

renovation projects were carried out in the Enugu metropolis' Ikirike, Agu-Owa, and Coal Camp.

The study also found that urban renewal strategies had differing effectiveness in the studied locations. Compared to Ikirike, the tactics worked better at Agu-Owa and Coal Camp. The study also showed that individuals along with environment of Enugu were affected by urban regeneration in both good and bad ways. These effects included things like property damage or loss, loss of livelihood, and household displacement; improvements to the environment; higher land values; better roads, buildings, and infrastructure; stability in the coal camp economy; and better employment prospects.

5.2 Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations were put forward for adoption.

1. Urban renewal projects should be embarked regularly to upgrade the living conditions in ageing and decaying urban centres in Enugu city and Enugu state. However, this should be implemented with full advice of town planners and other stakeholders.
2. The socioeconomic condition of slum dwellers should be improved to engender good reception of renewal schemes. This can be achieved through adequate education and economic empowerment programmes.
3. It is recommended that further review of renewed sites like Ikirike, Agu-Owa and Coal camp should be undertaken. This is to ensure that project objectives are realized.

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